

SYNTHESIS OF 2:4-DIMETHOXY- AND 2:4-DIHYDROXY-ISO-PHTHALIC ACIDS.

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The hitherto unknown 2:4-dihydroxyisophthalic acid and the corresponding 2:4-dimethoxyisophthalic acid have been synthesised by the oxidation of 2:4-dimethoxy-3-formylbenzoic acid, prepared by Shah and Laiwalla's modified Gattermann reaction, with alkaline potassium permanganate. The dimethoxy acid has been esterified and demethylated to the corresponding 2:4-dihydroxyisophthalic acid

Although 4:6-dimethoxyisophthalic acid and the corresponding dihydroxy acid has been known for a long time (Eijkman, Bergema, Henrard, *Chem. Zentr.*, 1905 I, 816) the isomeric 2:4-dihydroxyisophthalic acid and its dimethyl ether are hitherto unknown. The structure of 2:4-dihydroxyisophthalic acid was assigned to the product of carboxylation of β - or γ -resorcylic acids by heating them with ammonium carbonate and water in a sealed tube (Senhofer, Brunner, *Sitzungsber. A. Akad. Wiss. Wien*, 80, II, 504, 506). However, Späth, Klager and Schloseer (*Ber.*, 1932, 64, 2206) proved that this so-called 2:4-dihydroxyisophthalic acid was really the 4:6-dihydroxyisophthalic acid, identical with that prepared by Eijkman *et al* (*loc. cit.*).

Späth obtained 2:4-dimethoxyisophthalic acid as an oxidation product of osthol (Späth and Pesta, *Ber.*, 1934, 67, 853). He did not isolate the acid but he characterised it as the anilide which was prepared through the acid chloride. The obvious difficulty in the synthesis of such an acid is the introduction of COOH group in the '2' or γ -position. The introduction of CHO group in the '2' or γ -position had already been achieved by Shah and Laiwalla (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 1828). 2:4-Dimethoxy- and 2:4-dihydroxyisophthalic acids have been synthesised from the aldehyde.

Methyl 2:4-dihydroxy-3-formylbenzoate (I) is prepared by the modified Gattermann reaction (Shah and Laiwalla, *loc. cit.*) on methyl β -resorcyate. The dimethoxy derivative of the corresponding acid (II) is obtained by the methylation of the formyl ester. The dimethoxy acid is then oxidised with alkaline potassium permanganate to 2:4-dimethoxyisophthalic acid (III). This is then demethylated to 2:4-dihydroxyisophthalic acid (IV) by refluxing it with anhydrous aluminium chloride in benzene solution.

The dimethoxy acid on esterification with methyl alcohol and sulphuric acid affords a mixture of the mono and the dimethyl ester, viz., methyl 2:4-dimethoxy-3-carboxybenzoate (V, R=H and R'=Me) or 2:4-dimethoxy-3-carbomethoxybenzoic acid (V, R=Me and R=H), and methyl 2:4-dimethoxyisophthalate (V, R=R'=Me). The monomethyl ester is assumed to have the structure of methyl γ -2:4-dimethoxy-3-carboxybenzoate (V, R=H and R'=Me), as there is very little possibility of the carboxyl group in the '2' position of being esterified due to steric hindrance.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Methyl 2:4-dihydroxy-3-formylbenzoate (I) was prepared by the modified Gattermann reaction on methyl- β -resorcyate according to Shah and Laiwalla (*loc. cit.*) and was subsequently methylated to 2:4-dimethoxy-3-formylbenzoic acid (II) also according to the same authors.

Oxidation of 2:4-Dimethoxy-3-formylbenzoic Acid to 2:4-Dimethoxyisophthalic Acid (III).

—The oxidation of the formyl acid was attempted in different ways under different conditions with different quantities of potassium permanganate and using different solvents, and the following method was found to be the best.

2:4-Dimethoxy-3-formylbenzoic acid (5 g.) was dissolved in sodium hydroxide solution (50 c.c., 10%). Potassium permanganate (25 g.) was then added to the alkaline solution in small quantities at a time during about an hour, the mixture being cooled at intervals whenever necessary. At this stage, the solution turned pink, when sodium bisulphite (4 g.) was added to it to reduce the excess of potassium permanganate when the solution acquired a greenish tint. The manganese dioxide was filtered, the solution acidified with hydrochloric acid, concentrated and extracted with ether after salting. On the evaporation of ether a white solid was left which was dissolved in sodium bicarbonate solution (5%), acidified with hydrochloric acid and the salted solution again extracted with ether. A white solid, m.p. 218-20°, was obtained which crystallised from benzene in small shining micro-crystals, m.p. 222-23°, yield 0.6 g. (Found: C, 53.1; H, 4.3. $C_{10}H_{10}O_6$ requires C, 53.1; H, 4.4 per cent).

The precipitated manganese dioxide on boiling with sodium hydroxide (5%) and acidifying the alkaline filtrate with hydrochloric acid and subsequent extraction with ether, yielded some more quantity of the acid, total yield 0.8 g.

The acid gave effervescence with sodium bicarbonate solution and did not react with 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazine. It was very soluble in methyl and ethyl alcohols, acetone, and fairly soluble in hot water, from which it was crystallised in long needles, m.p. 220-21°.

Methyl 2:4-Dimethoxy-3-carboxybenzoate (V, R=H, and R'=Me) or *2:4-Dimethoxy-3-carbomethoxybenzoic acid* (V, R=Me; R'=H) and *Methyl 2:4-dimethoxyisophthalate* (V, R=R'=Me).

2:4-Dimethoxyisophthalic acid (0.4 g.) was dissolved in methyl alcohol (12 c.c.). Concentrated sulphuric acid (1.2 c.c., *d*, 1.84) was then slowly added to the solution and the mixture refluxed on a water-bath for 4 hours. At the end of the reaction, the reaction mixture was poured on to cold water, the solution salted and extracted with ether. The oily product obtained on the evaporation of the ether was treated with sodium bicarbonate solution (5%) and filtered. The insoluble portion, which was the dimethyl ester of the acid, crystallised in colourless long needles from hot water, m.p. 78-80°. (Found: C, 56.4; H, 5.3. $C_{12}H_{14}O_6$ requires C, 56.7; H, 5.5 per cent).

The sodium bicarbonate-soluble portion, which was the monomethyl ester of the acid, was recovered by acidifying the filtrate with hydrochloric acid and subsequent extraction with ether. The solid, obtained on the evaporation of the ether, crystallised in tiny pinkish needles from hot dilute alcohol, m.p. 150-51°. (Found: C, 54.4; H, 5.2. $C_{11}H_{12}O_6$ requires C, 55.0, H, 5.0 per cent). It gives effervescence with sodium bicarbonate solution and gives no colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride.

Demethylation of 2:4-Dimethoxyisophthalic Acid to 2:4-Dihydroxy-iso-phthalic acid (IV).—2:4-Dimethoxy-iso-phthalic acid (0.3 g.) was dissolved in petroleum ether and anhydrous aluminium chloride (1 g.) was added to the solution which was refluxed on a water-bath for 2 hours. The solution was then filtered and on the evaporation of the petroleum ether the aluminium chloride was decomposed with dilute hydrochloric acid (20 c.c., 1:1) and the solution salted and extracted with ether. On the evaporation of ether the colourless solid obtained was crystallised from hot water in tiny pinkish needles, m.p. 179-81°. (Found: C, 48.2; H, 3.2. $C_8H_6O_6$ requires C, 48.5; H, 3.0 per cent). It gives effervescence with sodium bicarbonate solution and a red colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride.

The preparation of the mono and the dimethyl esters of 2:4-dihydroxyisophthalic acid is being attempted.